

**ROLE OF SCHOOLS AND VOCATIONAL-TECHNICAL
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN DAILY LIFE OF VILLAGE
POPULATION (in case of Surkhandarya region between 1960 and 1980)**

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Annotation. In the article, it is written about the role of schools, vocational and technical educational institutes in daily life of rural residents of Surkhandarya region in the 1960-1980s, the construction and operation of village schools, and the existing problems of those educational institutes.

Key words: school, vocational educational institution, teacher, educator, student, pupil, manufacturing schools, school kitchen.

Laws "Full implementation of compulsory seven-year education in the Uzbek SSR" (1957) and "Strengthening the connection of school with life and further development of the public education system in the Uzbek SSR" (1959), adopted by the Supreme Council of the Uzbek SSR in the late 1950s played an important role in the increase of republican schools, especially schools in rural areas. Based on those laws, a number of rising changes were made in the education system. In particular, 7-year compulsory education was introduced in the school system, a number of high schools were converted into manufacturing (polytechnic) schools. From the 1961-1962 academic year, graduates from school were started to be given certificates of mastering additional specialties together with a certificate of secondary education[1.17]. That was a great opportunity for young people who graduated from school to work in various fields of agriculture. In that academic year, ninety eight 7-year schools in the region were completed and turned into 8-year schools, sixty secondary schools converted into manufacturing schools. In the 1960s, due to the lack of personnel in most schools in the rural areas of the region, well

educated young people who graduated from high school were hired as teachers in schools, and later they studied at educational institutions by correspondence and became specialists with secondary or higher education.

For instance, in 1961, out of 758 pedagogues working in Shorchi district, 249 had secondary education, 198 were studying part-time in the field of pedagogy, while 10,440 school teachers worked in regional schools, 1,680 from them with secondary education, 2,549 were studying part-time in the field of pedagogy [2.40].

According to the decision of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR dated March 29, 1960 "Establishment of general secondary education schools, special educational institutions and technical schools in the republic in one shift", a number of works were carried out in rural areas. In 1960, 1720 buildings around the republic, to be detailed 366 buildings in Surkhandarya were handed over to public education [3.80].

In the 1960s, schools in the region were built mainly at the expense of collective farm funds. In the 1959-1960 academic year, there were built 8 secondary schools where 4040 pupils could study and three 8-year schools in the region at the expense of collective farms, and the construction of thirty one schools where 11.840 pupils could study was continued. Fifteen of those schools were started in 1960-1961. In general, 186 schools were built at the expense of collective farms in Surkhandarya region in 1959-1964, and 76 schools where 24,000 pupils could study were built at the expense of collective farms in 1967-1972 [4.81]. Most of the village schools functioned in old and adapted buildings. In the academic year 1968-1969, 255 schools did not have electricity, 174 schools did not have kitchens. On February 12, 1960, the decision of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR "Implementation of the decision of the Council of Ministers of the USSR dated February 10, 1948 "On granting privileges to teachers of primary and 7-year schools" in the Surkhandarya region" established the task of providing housing and coal to teachers of schools in the rural areas of the region.

For that purpose, in 1962-1965, 829 houses were built for rural teachers in rural areas of the region, including 182 in Jarkurgan district, 125 in Sherabad district, 59 in Sariosiyo district, 46 in Termiz district, 69 in Denov district, and 355 in Shorchi district [5.113].

The main problem in rural schools was student dropout. In 1965, 19,000 students were accepted to the 1st grade in the region, and 10 years later, in 1973, 17,000 of them (89.1 percent) completed the 8th grade, and 2,000 students did not graduate for various reasons. In the 1971-1972 school year, 151 students from the rural areas of the Saryosi district, and in the 1972-1973 school year, 670 students from that district left the school [6,176].

Most of those who dropped out of school were girls, and in the villages of the region, especially in the mountainous areas, there was an old-fashioned view that "Education is not important for girls". For that reason, parents did not send girls to school after finishing the 8th grade, and in some cases even after finishing the 6th-7th grade. For example, in the 6th grade of the 1961-1962 academic year, 607 female students studied in the schools of Sherabad district, but by the 7th grade, their number decreased to 551, that is, 56 of them did not go to school in one academic year. The main reason why girls did not go to school was their early marriage. For example, in the 1966-1967 school year, more than hundred female pupils of the 8th grade in Denov district schools quitted attending school because of the early marriage [7.3]. In the 1957-1958 academic year, 5,000 female students were admitted to the 1st grade in the region, and ten years later, only 1,811 of them graduated from school. During that period, about 4,000 girls did not graduate from high school because the parents of girls who completed the 8th grade did not allow them to continue their studies. In the region, cases of students dropping out of school continued even in the 1970s. For example, during the 1971-1972 academic year, 600 pupils of regional schools left the school, and in the 1975-1976 academic year, 974 students lost contact with the school [8.39]. According to the decision of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR on August 8, 1973 "Development of the work of rural

general secondary schools", schools of rural areas were transferred into one shift. In the 1975-1976 academic year, 71% of regional schools had 1-shift teaching.

In the 1960s and 1970s, there was a great need for teachers in almost all subjects in rural schools. In the 1963-1964 academic year, 193 schools in rural areas lacked teachers for foreign language, 30 schools for music, 32 for art, 21 for chemistry and biology, and 20 for physics and mathematics [9.50]. Therefore, in many schools it became a common practice for teachers who were non-specialists to teach. For example, in the 1972-1973 academic year, the native language and literature teacher of secondary school No.54 of Sariosiyo district conducted mathematics and physics lessons also, while the art teacher of secondary school No.28 of Termiz district conducted chemistry and biology lessons at the same time [10.16]. Due to the lack of teachers in rural schools, some subjects were not taught at all, which in turn would be an obstacle for rural youth who wanted to enter a higher educational institution. That is why the students of the special one-year preparatory courses opened at the higher educational institutions of the republic since the 1960s were mostly rural youth [11.574].

By the 1980s, teacher-staffing problems had subsided, but school building problems remained. In 1983-1985, schools with 7,048 seats were built in rural areas, but 45 percent of rural schools operated in adapted buildings, 311 school classrooms did not have floors, more than 100 schools did not have a kitchen, and one out of three schools did not have a school canteen [12.2].

On the basis of the law of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR, adopted on December 24, 1958, "Strengthening the connection between school and life and on the further development of the system of public education in the USSR", 3-year vocational and technical educational institutions were established in order to provide vocational and technical education to young people living in the villages [13.130]. In 1971-1974, 6,300 rural youths graduated from regional technical educational institutions and graduated as tractor drivers, mechanics-drivers and other

professions. In 1975, ten vocational-technical educational institutions were in the region, in five of them regional agriculture experts were trained.

In 1982, the number of vocational and technical educational institutions in the region increased to 28, and in 1987 reached to 32. Twenty-five of them trained agricultural specialists. Vocational and technical educational institutions were neglected for years, that type of education was often overshadowed by secondary schools, technical schools and higher education institutions. In 1987, 12 of the 32 vocational and technical educational institutions in the region did not have a dormitory, and 8 did not have a kitchen. Commonly, Pupils with bad behavior and low mastery in schools were sent to vocational and technical educational institutions. The words of school principals and teachers to students, "If you don't study well, I will send you to vocational and technical educational institutions" created a bad image of those educational institutions in the minds of students, and they never wanted to go there [14.38].

Thus, in the 1960s-1980s, education of in schools, vocational and technical educational institutes, and pre-school educational institutions in Surkhandarya region was carried out mainly on the basis of instilling the idea of "developed socialism" into the minds of students and educating them in the communist spirit. During that period, educational institutions in rural areas of Surkhandarya region had problems such as ruining school buildings, girls dropping out of school, lack of teachers. The main goal of the Soviet government to increase the construction of preschool educational institutions in the countryside in the 1960s and 1970s was to prevent rural women with many children from being busy with raising children staying at home and to attract them more to agricultural work. However, during the studied period, educational institutions developed in the village, and played an important role in the spiritual and educational development of the new generation.

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